

IBA (Internationale Bauausstellung) Emscherpark – a successful attempt in Germany

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Like by a latter day St. Christopher, the state agencies for the preservation of industrial monuments in Northrhine-Westphalia have been taken up on the shoulders of the "International Building Exhibition - IBA" held in the Ruhrgebiet from 1989 to 1999. This meant a quantum leap in the possibilities to preserve industrial monuments like historic ironworks, coal mines and power stations.

After nearly twenty years of listing those objects since 1970 and nearly automatically reaching larger dimensions following the course of the industrial revolution, IBA enabled preservation strategies involving much more funding possibilities. This scale however implied also certain dangers for the large-scale objects: looking for some kind of difficult-to-achieve profitability, the range of alterations to the structures has grown considerably, thus endangering the documentary character of the sites with regard to the authentic stories they are expected to tell. This can be exemplified with buildings like Jahrhunderthalle in Bochum or Zollverein XII mine (a world heritage site) in Essen, where contemporary uses have led to a considerable threat to the original substance. IBA nevertheless has come up with a considerable improvement in the self-assessment of the Ruhrgebiet and the way this region is perceived in Germany and abroad.